

The background of the slide is a photograph of the interior of the SNO+ detector. It shows a large, spherical structure with a complex network of optical fibers and photomultiplier tubes, illuminated with a blue light. The fibers are arranged in a dense, web-like pattern, and the overall scene is filled with a sense of depth and complexity.

The SNO+ Experiment
NuPhys 2026
Daniel Cookman

The SNO+ Experiment

Successor to the SNO Experiment

2km underground at SNOLAB: ~3 muon/hour

12m diameter Acrylic Vessel (AV)

>9000 PMTs

Ultra-Pure Water Shielding

Varying Target:
I. Water
II. LAB Scintillator
III. Tellurium Loading

JINST 16 P08059 (2021)

A Multi-Purpose Neutrino Experiment

Solar Neutrinos

Neutrinoless
Double Beta Decay

Reactor & Geo-Neutrinos

Supernova Neutrinos
& Exotics

SNO+ Timeline

We are here!

Water Phase:
Nitrogen cover gas
used to minimise
backgrounds

Partial-Fill Phase:
Scintillator over water
Fill paused due to
COVID

Scintillator Phase:

- LAB liquid scintillator
- +2.2 g/L PPO fluor
- +2.2 mg/L bis-MSB wavelength shifter

Next:
Tellurium-loaded
Phase for $0\nu\beta\beta$

Water Phase Measurements

World-leading nucleon-decay limits:
PRD 110, 122003 (2024)

Decay mode	Partial lifetime limit	Existing limits
n	9.0×10^{29} y	5.8×10^{29} y [5]
p	9.6×10^{29} y	3.6×10^{29} y [6]
pp	1.1×10^{29} y	4.7×10^{28} y [6]
np	6.0×10^{28} y	2.6×10^{28} y [6]
nn	1.5×10^{28} y	1.4×10^{30} y [5]

Very deep overburden & low radioactivity in water phase enabled a variety of measurements in SNO+!

Low-background solar ^8B flux measurement: PRD 110, 122003 (2024)

Cosmogenic neutron production in water: ArXiv:2511.04600

Antineutrinos in Water

Antimatter neutrinos detected from a nuclear reactor 240 km away

- First evidence of reactor antineutrinos in a Cherenkov detector: 3.5σ
- Taking advantage of lowest-ever energy threshold for a large Cherenkov detector: ~ 1.4 MeV

- 190 days livetime
- Two analysis methods gave comparable results: Likelihood ratio & Boosted Decision Tree

Directionality in Scintillator

PRD 109, 072002 (2024)

- Scintillation light is isotropic, so reconstructing direction is hard...
- ...But not impossible! Cherenkov light still present if you look carefully:

- Data from partial fill & early scint phases, where PPO loading low (0.6 g/L), leading to slow scintillation: good separation with Cherenkov light
- First event-by-event reconstruction of direction on high light yield scintillator!

Solar Neutrino Flux & Oscillations in Scintillator

- Analysis of ^8B ES interactions in initial 143.1 livedays of scint. phase data

- Cosmogenic & External backgrounds become negligible in strict fiducial volume: possible future sensitivity < 3 MeV!
- Possible analysis techniques to remove dominant ^{208}Tl background:
 $(5.3 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{-17} \text{ g/g } ^{232}\text{Th}$ in 4m radial volume

Solar Neutrino Flux & Oscillations in Scintillator

- Parallel analyses for measuring flux and neutrino oscillation parameters

- Oscillation measurement complementary to reactor analysis: possible first-ever combined fit from the same detector?

Solar osc. fit result assumes global fit flux

Charged-Current Interactions on ^{13}C

PRL 135, 241803 (2025)

- CC interaction of solar neutrinos on ^{13}C possible, but as-yet unobserved
- Significance: 4.2σ
- **See Gulliver Milton's talk Thursday Session 2 for more!**

First ever measurement of this interaction by solar vs (second-ever in general!)

- Measured cross-section:

$$\langle \sigma(E_\nu) \rangle = (16.1_{-6.7}^{+8.5}(\text{stat.})_{-2.7}^{+1.6}(\text{syst.})) \times 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^2$$

Antineutrinos in Scintillator

ArXiv:2511.11856

- Precision measurement of Δm_{21}^2 from reactor antineutrinos using 685.2 days of data
- First ever measurement of geoneutrino flux in Western Hemisphere
- **See Will Parker's talk on Friday morning for more details!**

Searching for $0\nu\beta\beta$ in SNO+

NIMA 1051 168204 (2023)

- ^{130}Te to be loaded into scintillator to search for $0\nu\beta\beta$, via novel, scalable technique

Butanediol Purification Plant (Underground)
Commissioned

DDA Purification Plant (Surface)
Commissioned

Te-BD Synthesis
(Underground)
Commissioning

Telluric Acid Purification Plant (Underground)
Commissioned

Searching for $0\nu\beta\beta$ in SNO+

- No enrichment needed, high Q-value, long $2\nu\beta\beta$ half-life (lower intrinsic background)

- Initial loading planned for 2026
- Expected sensitivity after 3 years of loading 0.5% natTe: 1.8×10^{26} yr (90% CL)

ROI: 2.42 - 2.56 MeV $[-0.5\sigma - 1.5\sigma]$
Counts/Year: 9.68

Searching for $0\nu\beta\beta$ in SNO+

PRD 104 012002 (2021)
NIMA 1051 168204 (2023)

- Higher loadings of Te planned for SNO+
- Sensitivity with 5 years with 1.5% natTe loading:
 $T_{1/2} > 7.4 \times 10^{26}$ years (90% CL)
- Good light yield & stability found at higher loadings during R&D

Summary

- The SNO+ Experiment has taken water-phase data, and is currently taking scintillator-phase data
- Variety of analyses ongoing! A sample:
 - First ever observation of solar neutrinos interacting on ^{13}C (See Gulliver's talk)
 - Precision measurement of Δm^2_{21} & first ever measurement of geoneutrino flux in Western Hemisphere (See Will's talk)
 - ^8B Solar neutrino oscillation analysis underway with energy threshold < 3 MeV
- See also: Scott DeGraw's talk on using ML in SNO+ for PMT Calibration, Thursday Session 1
- Major preparations underway for planned Te-loading starting next year!

On behalf of the SNO+ Collaboration...

Thank You!

Backup Slides

Other SNO+ Publications

- Nucleon decay searches in water phase:
PRD 99, 032008 (2019)
PRD 105, 112012 (2022)
- Partial-fill antineutrino analysis:
EPJC 85 1 17 (2025)
- Water phase optical calibration:
JINST 16 P10021 (2021)
- Water phase neutron-capture calibration:
PRC 102 014002 (2020)
- SNO+ scintillator:
JINST 16 P05009 (2021)

Cosmogenic Neutrons in Water

ArXiv:2511.04600

- Extreme depth & cleanliness of SNO+ in water-phase allowed for measurement of neutron captures generated by cosmic-ray muons
- 321 days of data, 13690 μ s, 1412 neutrons
- AmBe source used for calibration

- Measured neutron yield: $(3.38^{+0.23}_{-0.30}) \times 10^{-4} \text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1} \mu^{-1}$
- In line with FLUKA predictions; GEANT4 differs by 30%
- Previous SNO measurement made in heavy water; plan to also measure in LS!

Solar Neutrino Flux, Water Phase

PRD 99, 012012 (2019)
PRD 110, 122003 (2024)

- Updated analysis with 126.6 kt-day exposure
- Includes 190 days of data with lowest background for a water Cherenkov detector > 5 MeV:
 0.32 ± 0.07 evs/kt-day

Results:

- Using 3.5 MeV threshold; large uncertainties in first bin
- Fitted flux consistent with other experiments after inclusion of oscillations:

$$(5.36_{-0.39}^{+0.41}(\text{stat.})_{-0.16}^{+0.17}(\text{syst.})) \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

Antineutrinos in SNO+

- Electron antineutrinos interact with protons via inverse beta decay
- Most antineutrinos come from Canadian reactors, 240-350 km away: ~ 100 reactor IBD events/year expected, after oscillations
- ~ 25 geoneutrino IBD events/year
- Dominant background are (α, n) interactions, α coming dominantly from ^{210}Po

